

Thinking about the types of contributions dashboards, how likely are you to use the following information disaggregated by gender/affiliation. Please explain.

- Number of contributors:

By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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Pull requests

- Pull request count

By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- Days to merge pull requests

By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- The proportion of pull request count

By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- The evolution over time of the number of pull requests

By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- Is there any other pull request information you would like to see?

Issues

- Issues count

By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- Days to issue first attention
By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- The proportion of issue count
By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- The evolution over time of the number of issues
By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- Is there any other issue information you would like to see?

StackOverflow

- StackOverflow Q&A count

By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- The average of accepted StackOverflow answers

By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- The proportion of StackOverflow Q&A count

By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- The evolution over time of StackOverflow Q&A

By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- Is there any other stackoverflow information you would like to see?
- Are there any other ways you would use the types of contribution dashboards that we did not cover? Are there any other information you would like to see in these dashboards?

